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Preliminary Studies Comparing Electrogeneration by a Bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in a Microbial Fuel Cell

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Abstract

Global energy crisis coupled with environmental pollutions have warranted a surge in greener energy alternatives, of which microbial fuel cells (MFCs) is considered to be a good alternative. Unfortunately, MFC suffers setback as a result of low current generation and poor efficiency. Use of microbial consortia as inoculum is another way of enhancing the efficiency and current generation of MFC. Different inocula, namely: anaerobic sludge from domestic waste water and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Baker's yeast) were tested as biocatalysts for electricity generation in MFC using yoghurt waste water (YWW) as substrate with the plain YWW serving as control. The maximum power densities generated are 1.93mW/m² (current density, 4.43mA/m²), 0.32mW/m² (current density, 0.81mA/m²) and 0.23mW/m² (current density, 0.81mA/m²) for anaerobic sludge, Baker's yeast and plain YWW, respectively. This study showed that anaerobic sludge can be a perfect choice relative to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* or plain yoghurt waste water as a biocatalyst for electricity production in microbial fuel cell. The study has also shown the potentials of microbial fuel cell as a promising alternative and green technology for waste water treatment.

Keywords: Electricity, Microorganisms, Green Energy, Fuel cell, Bacteria

Introduction

The dependence on fossil fuel as a primary source of energy is faced with three challenges: (1) the global demands for energy are increasing and fossil fuel cannot be a sustainable or renewable source; (2) the continuous consumption of fossil fuels are accompanied with the release of greenhouse gases which present hazards to human health and other living organisms within the surroundings; and (3) the cost of affording it by people especially the poor (Chaturvedi & Verma, 2016; Venkata Mohan *et al.*, 2008). This therefore necessitates the search for alternative sources of energy that are renewable and environmentally as well as economically friendly. Microbial fuel cells (MFCs) are considered as a better option to address such challenges. An MFC utilizes organic matter as substrate which is a renewable source. Moreover, the method use to release the energy is a fermentation (biological) process which is environmentally friendly (Venkata Mohan *et al.*, 2008).

Microbial fuel cells (MFCs) are a form of electrochemical cell which harnesses the metabolic activity of microorganisms to generate electricity by direct or mediated transfer of the electrons released from the organic matter (substrate) they oxidized (Logan, 2009; Oh & Min, 2004). MFCs comprise of two compartments, namely: the anode and cathode compartment (Oh & Min, 2004). The microorganisms reside in the anode compartment where they oxidize the organic matter they are provided with and finally generating three products; carbon dioxide, protons and more importantly electrons. The released electrons are conducted by the anode via the electrochemical circuit into the cathode compartment, while the protons pass into the cathode compartment through a cationic membrane and finally combine with the electrons and electrons acceptor (specifically oxygen atom from the air to form H₂O) (Jatoi *et al.*, 2018; Logan, 2009). The flow of the electrons through the circuit generates an electric current which can be harnessed by placing a load (bulb) between the two electrodes (anode and cathode) (Chaturvedi & Verma, 2016).

Materials and Methods

Substrate preparation:

Yoghurt waste water was collected from yoghurt product line at Majestic Dairy Product Birnin Kudu. It was then stored at low temperature in a refrigerator

Several studies have been conducted on microbial fuel cells (MFCs) to generate electricity, utilizing wide variety of feedstock and inoculum (Cercado-Quezada *et al.*, 2010). Research is continued in finding the best candidate microorganism and feedstock for electricity generation. Cercado-Quezada (2010) together with his associates has tested three different food industry wastes for electricity generation which include: fermented apple juice, wine lees and yoghurt waste. The inoculums they used are Anaerobic Sludge (AS) and Garden Compost (GC), of which the AS - MFC had been found to produce higher power density with YW than the rest of the inoculums and substrates (Cercado-Quezada *et al.*, 2010). Jatoi and his co-workers utilized *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* with distillery effluent at different organic load and substrate concentrations and has obtained a maximum power and current density of 69mW/m² and 82.48mA/m² respectively (Jatoi *et al.*, 2018). On another side, Sayed and collaborators have investigated the catalytic activity of baker's yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in a mediatorless microbial fuel cell and was found to be electroactive with greater ability to form biofilm on the anode surface (Sayed *et al.*, 2012).

A wide range of waste water especially from food processing industries have been utilized as feedstock in microbial fuel cells as a means to treat the waste water. However, the power output is too low if the purpose is to be solely for electricity generation. This issue may be attributed to the low organic matters present in most waste waters that are utilizable by the electroactive bacteria (Rabaey *et al.*, 2003). Yoghurt waste water is distinguished by its high organic matter content (Cristian, 2010; Slavov, 2017) which is highly biodegradable. However, the best candidate microorganism to utilize it as a substrate and generate electricity in a microbial fuel cell is yet to be found. In this study, we therefore compare the electrogenic potentials of bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in a microbial fuel cell, using yoghurt waste water as substrate with a goal of establishing a basis for identifying the best candidate microorganism for electricity generation in microbial fuel cell.

before use. For each time of use, pH was first checked and balanced to 7.0 using KOH. 500ml was transferred to 5 separate MFC anode chambers.

Inoculum Preparation:

The MFC inocula were prepared as follows:

Anaerobic Sludge: A domestic waste water was collected and subjected to anaerobic condition in a tightly sealed 500ml bottle flask at 37°C for about 15 days based on the procedure reported by (Cercado-Quezada *et al.*, 2010). Glucose solution was added daily using syringe through the bottle cap. This allowed the bacteria in the sludge to multiply and establish itself into anaerobic condition.

Baker's yeast (*S. cerevisiae*): baker's yeast was bought from local market and was activated according to the procedure performed by (Sayed *et al.*, 2012). 0.13g sample of the dried yeast was added into 100ml of distilled water containing 0.5g glucose, 2g of peptone, 1g of malt extract and 1g of yeast extract. The mixture was incubated at around 30°C for 16 hours.

MFC Construction:

The MFC construction was performed based on the design described by (Logan, 2004). Five (5) pairs of

cylindrical rubbers with tightly covered lids were purchased from local market and were used to construct an improvised MFC chambers. Each pair was connected using an improvised salt bridge made by filling half inch PVC pipe with dissolved mixture of NaCl and Agar that form a gel within the pipe. The improvised agar-salt salt bridge connected each pair through a hole made after 1.5inch distance above the bottom level of each rubber. Copper and platinum wires (Purchased from *Shugaba Scientific Equipment and General Enterprise, Katsina Road, Opposite Federal Secretariat Kano*) were used as anode and cathode electrode respectively. Carbon rods obtained from 1.5V dry cell batteries were arranged and tighten using a clip round each copper wire to increase the surface area of the anode electrode to about an estimate of $4.965 \times 10^{-3} \text{m}^2$. A hole was made at the center of each lid that fit the copper wire for the anode chamber lid and platinum wire for the cathode chamber lid. Two other holes were made on the cathode chamber lid for air circulation (one for air sparging and the other for air to leave the chamber) (See figure 1 below for the materials improvised in electrodes construction).

Figure 1: A. is a platinum wire that is inserted into the cathode chamber serving as cathode electrode; B. are carbons rods (of 1.5v dry cell battery) arranged and tightened round a copper wire (C) to be inserted into the anode chamber and serve as anode electrode.

MFC Fermentation

For the 5 pairs of the MFC chambers. The anode chambers were filled with 500ml of the prepared substrate (yoghurt waste water) and two third of the volume of the cathode chambers were filled with tap water. The anode chambers were inoculated as follows:

1st Pair: inoculated with 10ml of anaerobic sludge and 2g of glucose;

2nd Pair: inoculated with 10ml of anaerobic sludge alone;

3rd Pair: inoculated with 10ml of activated yeast and 2g of glucose;

4th Pair: inoculated with 10ml of the activated yeast alone;

5th Pair: the yoghurt waste water was left with its indigenous bacteria alone.

The anode and cathode electrodes in each pair were connected with wire to complete each circuit, after which

they are maintained at temperature of about 37°C using water bath.

Measurements

The MFCs after incubation were allowed to stabilize overnight starting from 8:00pm. The voltage and current readings were taking using multimeter at every interval of two (2) hours starting from 8:00am. This was performed by opening the circuit and connecting the multimeter leads in series with the circuit and the readings were recorded after a stable value was achieved at each time interval. The anode chamber was shaken each time prior to measurements.

Theory/Calculations

The experiment with each inoculum was divided in to two: one was using the yoghurt waste alone as source of energy for the microbes in the inoculum while the other was with glucose addition. The aim was to evaluate the

capacity of the microbe in each inoculum to utilize yoghurt waste as its source of energy. The voltage and current readings were taking in millivolt and milli-ampere respectively using multimeter at each interval of 2 hours. In each case, the power is calculated using the equation below:

$$power (mW) = \frac{current (mA) \times voltage (mV)}{10^{-3}} \dots\dots\dots(I)$$

The anodic total surface area was calculated to be $A = 0.004965m^2 \dots\dots\dots(II)$

This was used to calculate the current and power density of the MFC at each current and voltage measured using the equations below:

$$current\ density = \frac{current}{anodic\ surface\ area} \dots\dots\dots(III)$$

$$power\ density = \frac{power}{anodic\ surface\ area} \dots\dots\dots(IV)$$

Where; the anodic surface area is in (m^2), current in (mA), current density in (mA/m^2), power in (mW) and the power density in (mW/m^2).

Three inocula were tested according to the above experimental set-ups. They include: (1) Anaerobic

sludge (A.S), (2) Baker’s Yeast (B.Y) and (3) Free Yoghurt Waste Water which served as control to ascertain the amount of electricity production that may result from the activity of the indigenous bacteria (I.B) in the yoghurt waste water and was used as a basis to evaluate the potentials of the microbes from the other inocula.

The microbial fuel cells (MFCs) performance is defined by the degree of electricity production in terms of power densities (P). In this regard, the results of electricity production using the three different inoculums were analyzed in two different ways:

- a) The power densities produced using each inoculum were analyzed for significant difference in the presence or absence of glucose in addition to the yoghurt waste water;
- b) The power densities produced using the three inoculums were analyzed together for significant differences between one another;

All statistical analysis were conducted using Microsoft excel and results were obtained at 95% confidence.

Results

Results of the MFC performance for the two different inocula as well as the control (Intrinsic yoghurt bacteria) were analyzed and presented graphically in figure 2, 3 & 4.

Figure 2 represent the microbial fuel cell performance of Anaerobic sludge in the presence and absence of glucose supplement. Figure 3 represent the microbial fuel cell performance of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in the presence and absence of glucose supplement. As can be seen from both figure 2&3, significance rise in power densities were observed in the presence of glucose. However, a nearly uniform power production was attained and maintained for some time in the absence of glucose supplement. Taking figure 2 as an example, it can be seen that the microbial fuel cell performance rise to a significant height at the initial, but could not maintain the power production at such peak. A significant falling and rising was observed which could be interpreted as the microbial attempt to switch from utilizing glucose as substrate to utilizing the organic matter presence in the yoghurt waste water. Initially the microorganisms

would definitely want to use glucose as an immediate energy source. However, upon exhausting the little amount of the glucose they were supplemented with, they would have to switch and adapt to the alternative source they found available (organic matter present in the yoghurt waste water in this case) and in the process of doing that they become inactive for some time, after which they pick-up gain; attaining a high performance again. Unlike in the absence of glucose supplement when the microorganism had to adapt to utilize yoghurt waste water as their source of energy in the beginning. Thus, no such fluctuation in power production was observed (figure 2).

Figure 2: MFC performance using Anaerobic sludge (A.S) in the presence or absence of Glucose.

Figure 3: MFC performance using *S. cerevisiae* (Baker's Yeast, B.Y) in the presence or absence of Glucose.

Figure 4 illustrates the differences in microbial fuel cell performance between anaerobic sludge, intrinsic yoghurt bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The result has shown that anaerobic sludge produces significantly higher microbial fuel cell performance followed by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, with indigenous yoghurt bacteria becoming the last in performance. It can also be seen that a closely uniform power production has only been attained with anaerobic sludge (figure 2&4).

This result is an indication that anaerobic sludge may be rich in electroactive microbial consortia that are capable of continuous transfer of electrons directly to the conducting electrode. It's also an indication that the microorganisms present in the sludge could better utilize the organic matter present in the yoghurt waste water than indigenous yoghurt bacteria and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Figure 4: MFC performance using Anaerobic sludge (A.S) from domestic sewage, *S. cerevisiae* (the Baker's Yeast, B.Y) and the Intrinsic Bacteria (I.B) presence in yoghurt waste water.

Conclusion

The maximum power densities generated are 1.93mW/m² (at current density, 4.43mA/m²), 0.32mW/m² (at 0.81mA/m²) and 0.23mW/m² (at 0.81mA/m²) using anaerobic sludge from domestic sewage, Baker's yeast and Indigenous bacteria of yoghurt waste respectively. Although, the general power outputs may be appreciably low compared to those from previous literatures, the objectives of the research have been achieved; anaerobic sludge has been found to have high potential as inoculum for electricity production in microbial fuel cell, using yogurt waste

water as substrate. The low current productions might be the result of several factors that include the microbial fuel cell chamber construction, choice of electrode materials as well as human and environmental factors in the course of measurement. However, these were general to all the test conducted and thus, could not affect the outcome of the objective of the research.

Recommendation

Recommendations are that, further studies need to be conducted to optimize the microbial fuel cell performance using the same inocula and substrates. Since anaerobic sludge from domestic waste water has proven to produce greater power output in comparison with other inocula, further studies should be performed to isolate and identify the specific or consortia of

microorganisms responsible for the greater microbial fuel cell performance.

Authors Contributions

All authors participate actively in the development of this work; either in the study design, data collection, data analyses, data interpretation or writing this manuscript and in the decision to publish results.

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